

RESEARCH ARTICLE

On the Identification of Thyroid Nodules using Semi-Supervised Deep Learning

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Summary

Detecting malign cases from thyroid nodule examinations is crucial in healthcare particularly to improve the early detection of such cases. However, malign thyroid nodules can be extremely rare and is hard to find using the traditional rule based or expert-based methods. For this reason, the solutions backed by Machine Learning (ML) algorithms are key to improve the detection rates of such rare cases. In this paper, we investigate the application of ML in the healthcare domain for the detection of rare thyroid nodules. The utilized dataset is collected from 636 distinct patients in 99 unique days in Turkey. In addition to the texture feature data of the Ultrasound (US), we have also included the scores of different assessment methods created by different health institutions (e.g., Korean, American and European thyroid societies) as additional features. For detection of extremely rare malign cases, we use auto-encoder based neural network model. Through numerical results, it is shown that the auto-encoder based model can result in an average *Recall* score of 0.98 and a *Sensitivity* score of 1.00 for detecting malign and non-malign cases from the healthcare dataset outperforming the traditional classification algorithms that are trained after Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) oversampling.

KEYWORDS:

auto-encoder, semi-supervised deep learning, thyroid nodule, classification, malign

1 | INTRODUCTION

Thyroid Ultrasound (US) is highly requested in the clinic since it provides a perspective to perform differential diagnosis of thyroid nodules which are solid or fluid-filled lumps or growths in the thyroid gland as depicted in Fig 1. Nevertheless, despite all the usefulness of the US along with other diagnostic methods, it is still very difficult to decide whether a thyroid nodule is benign or malignant, which makes the identification of thyroid nodules a highly important task. One of the underlying reasons for this difficulty is that the changes that cells show in the cancerization stages are also seen during some normal processes of the cells. For instance, in the initial stages of the cancerization, cellular differentiation takes place in which thyroid cells gradually lose their normal cell features, which is a phenomena called atypia. However, atypia may also appear when a cell degenerates as a normal event or when it has an infection causing changes in cell response, which may cause the cell to be perceived as malignant. Mostly, thyroid nodules are close to benign in nature¹. The aim in the clinic is to detect the remaining abnormal cases.

There are some features, such as echo, size, peripheral halo, calcification, shape-contour, that constitute as risk indicators in radiology when evaluating the nodules in thyroid US images². Risk classifications have been defined by interpreting these

features³. For example, spongy nodule is a finding that lowers the malignancy risk, whereas presence of microcalcification is an important feature to detect malignancy. Shape-contour is another feature where distorted contour or nodules with irregular edges are significant for malignancy. The nodules that are taller in shape instead of being wide point out a finding regarding the extension of the lesion. Taller nodules are meaningful for malignancy. As a final example, if there is a Lymphadenopathy (LAP), it is suspected for an accompanying malignancy.

In the interventional radiology, sample cells are collected from the nodules by a method of Fine Needle Aspiration (FNA) operation⁴, when the analysis on the US points out a malignancy risk for these nodules. After the FNA, pathology unit performs investigation on these collected cells and reports that if there is a malignancy risk or not based on the Bethesda classification system⁵. If sufficient evidence is found in the pathological analysis, it can be clarified whether it is benign or malign according to Bethesda classification system. Nonetheless, there may be some cases in which the exact diagnosis can still not be given even after the pathological examination due to the insufficient sample in the FNA, which may occur when the number of sample cells is intentionally limited, considering that it is harmful for the patient to collect a lot of tissue cells, and thus the cancerous cells may not exist on the collected tissue samples. In some risky situations, the pathology unit may require to collect extra samples from the patient for further analysis, which means both a waste of time for the treatment and an extra operation for the patient. Therefore, identifying the nodules correctly without the need for repeating FNA process will provide great gain in terms of treatment. Machine Learning (ML) techniques are popularly used to solve important and challenging identification problems. However, applying the correct technique to the right problem is critical to obtain efficient and near-accurate results.

This paper proposes a novel approach and solution to the considered problem of the identification of `mal_ign` (abnormal) cases. To this end, an auto-encoder based neural network is proposed to reconstruct and classify `mal_ign` cases. More specifically, the auto-encoder based neural network performs a self-supervised learning by encoding the patient's tissue sample characteristics of the input data as fixed-size vectors. This encoded representation is later used by the decoder to reconstruct the input data. The decoder network is capable of outputting accurate output data and classify the data. Through numerical results, the proposed auto-encoder based neural network model is shown to have an average *Recall* score of 0.98 and a *Sensitivity* score of 1.00 for all `mal_ign` and `non-mal_ign` cases of the healthcare dataset outperforming the other traditional classification algorithms after Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) oversampling are performed in the training dataset.

2 | RELATED WORK AND MOTIVATION

In the literature, ML based analysis are mostly used for the detection of thyroid nodules on the US images. The study in⁶ developed a multitask cascade convolution neural network (MC-CNN) framework to exploit the context information of thyroid nodules. In⁷, the authors present a method for diagnosing benign and malignant thyroid nodules using combined conventional US and US elasticity imaging based on a convolutional neural network. The article in⁸ aims to compare the performance of

FIGURE 1 An illustration of a nodule on the thyroid tissue.

radiomics and deep learning based methods for the classification of thyroid nodules from ultrasound images. An automatic system is developed in⁹ that classifies the thyroid images and segments the thyroid gland using machine learning algorithms with classifiers such as Support Vector Machine (SVM). These studies focus on applying ML techniques to the images. In contrast, in this study we use the dimensional textual data of the thyroid nodules to perform ML analysis.

In the articles^{10,11}, applying ML techniques to characterize the soft tissues is presented, but the article does not have focus on thyroid nodules and malignancy detection perspective. The review¹² is presented that summarizes the available literature data on texture analysis, with and without Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD), in patients with suspected thyroid nodules or differentiated thyroid cancer. A deep-learning approach on the limited number of ultrasound text classifiers for predicting benign and malignant thyroid nodules is presented in¹³. Deep learning is implemented on a limited healthcare dataset. The authors in¹⁴ applied one ML technique which is Random Forrest Classifier (RFC) algorithm to perform classification of the thyroid nodules. Similarly, the study in¹⁵ run RFC and present the important classifiers in the textual dataset. The study in¹⁶ developed and validated a ML based radiomics model for evaluating immunohistochemical characteristics in patients with suspected thyroid nodules. The article in¹⁷ extended the evaluation with ML and added the SVM technique to their analysis. Unfortunately, these articles present a classification with applying ML for thyroid nodes rather than making a definitive or near-definitive diagnosis. These previous studies are based on the classifying by nature of the selected and applied ML algorithm. A more concrete approach is needed with ML on the obtained big data in cases where the detection of the malignancy is so critical in terms of reducing the FNA process applied to the patients.

To the best of our knowledge, the general problem of identifying extremely rare malign cases of thyroid nodules has not previously been studied with textual data collected from patients along with broad range of feature vectors that include previous decisions of rule based approaches of various thyroid societies such as Korean, American and European. Our contributions in this paper can be described as follows;

- We collected US data from patients retrospectively with suspicious thyroid disease, constituted a dataset and validated the malignancy of the nodules with pathology results of FNAs.
- Due to imbalanced nature of the dataset, we utilized a semi-supervised ML approach based on utilization of auto-encoders to detect the extremely rare malign cases on the thyroid nodule textual data.
- In addition to the texture feature data of the US in our own dataset, we have also included the scores of different assessment methods created by different health institutions (e.g. European Thyroid Association (EU-Tirads), Korean Society of Thyroid Radiology (K-Tirads), American College of Radiology (ACR), American Thyroid Association (ATA)). As far as the authors knowledge, this is the first study in which these features were added to the texture data for the training of a ML algorithm to detect the malign cases.
- Experimental results show that the auto-encoder based neural network model can result in an average *Recall* score of 0.99 and a *Sensitivity* score of 1.00 for detecting malign and non-malign cases from the healthcare dataset outperforming the other compared classification algorithms that are trained with SMOTE oversampling method.

3 | METHODOLOGY

3.1 | System Overview

Our proposal for the detection of rare malign cases is built on using semi-supervised ML approach on top of observations on the data that is collected from treated patients. Fig. 2 illustrates an overview of the overall process of the proposed flow. First, the clinical samples (including the pathology, experience based risk scoring and texture data) are collected so that some those samples are fed into the training modules (both auto-encoder and classification algorithms) as the input and some into inference module for detection of the extremely rare malign cases. After data collection, whole data is put into pre-processing module. Inside the pre-processing module, the data is cleansed by omitting some of the features and training, validation and test datasets are created using SMOTE oversampling method in step-1. During training phase, all training and validation data samples are fed into the auto-encoder neural network as well as into ML classification algorithms (e.g. RFC, Decision Tree (DT) classifier, etc) in step-2. After model is created, model is deployed into inference module in step-3. Inside inference module, detection of malign cases can be done by passing the unseen test data into the auto-encoder as well as the ML classification models. A more detailed explanations of training and testing processes are provided in next sections.

FIGURE 2 Basic structure of the retrospective data collection and ML training methodology using auto-encoder based neural networks and ML classification algorithms.

3.2 | Semi-Supervised Learning with Auto-encoders

Semi-supervised learning is a subfield that combines both supervised and unsupervised learning. In semi-supervised learning, there are huge amounts of unlabelled data and small amount of labelled data. The unlabelled data is used to learn the representations of data whereas supervised learning method is used for training purposes, i.e. to classify the dataset into respective classes. In certain problems, using auto-encoders in semi-supervised learning is useful. An auto-encoder consists of three main modules: encoder, embedding and decoder as depicted in Figure 3. The encoder encodes the data into fixed dimension embedding and decoder act as the mirror image of encoder and transforms the embedding into original input. The number of layers (i.e. hidden layers) in both encoder and decoder are parts of the deep auto-encoders. The number of node in each layer is generally kept inversely proportional to the number of layers. The embedding or code dimension in the middle of encoder and decoder usually has less number of nodes that the input size. The loss function is selected to be binary cross entropy (for categorical inputs) or Mean Squared Error (MSE) (for numerical inputs).

An auto-encoder is trained to create a copy its input to its output. During this process, it also maps the input onto a latent vector. For example, given a dataset from a classification problem, an auto-encoder first encodes the input data into lower dimensional latent representation and later decodes the latent representation back into the input data. In other words, the decoder network in the auto-encoder attempts to reconstruct the original input signal. The learning is done by compressing the data during minimization of the reconstruction error. Later, a classification module uses Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) output layer to classify the input (under two categories, *malign* or *non-malign* in our problem).

The encoder and the decoder parts can be seen as two functions, denoted by ϕ and ψ respectively, such that the encoder maps the original data \mathcal{X} to a latent space \mathcal{F} , whereas ψ maps the latent space \mathcal{F} at the bottleneck to the output. Therefore, an auto-encoder is actually composition of the encoder and the decoder functions, i.e. $(\psi \circ \phi)$. Since these two functions perform the opposite of each other, the output of the auto-encoder becomes similar to its input, yet there occurs an error during reconstruction. Then, an auto-encoder which tries to minimize this error can formally be expressed as in (1).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \phi &: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{F} \\
 \psi &: \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{X} \\
 \phi, \psi &= \arg \min_{\phi, \psi} \| \mathcal{X} - (\psi \circ \phi) \mathcal{X} \|^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

More specifically, for an auto-encoder with 5 hidden layers as shown in Figure 3, the first hidden layer of the encoder part takes the input $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n = \mathcal{X}$ and maps it to $\mathbf{h}^1 \in \mathbb{R}^{m^1}$ which is then taken as input by the subsequent hidden layer. The output of

FIGURE 3 Architecture of an auto-encoder with 5 hidden layers.

the second hidden layer is similarly treated by the third hidden layer. This process is formulated in neural network denotation as in (2):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}^1 &= \sigma(\mathbf{W}^1 \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{b}^1) \\ \mathbf{h}^2 &= \sigma(\mathbf{W}^2 \mathbf{h}^1 + \mathbf{b}^2) \\ \mathbf{h}^3 &= \sigma(\mathbf{W}^3 \mathbf{h}^2 + \mathbf{b}^3) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where σ is an element-wise activation function that defines output of a node for a given input or set of inputs, $\mathbf{W}^1, \mathbf{W}^2, \mathbf{W}^3$ are weight matrices of the first, second and third hidden layers respectively, and $\mathbf{b}^1, \mathbf{b}^2, \mathbf{b}^3$ are bias vectors of the first, second and third hidden layers respectively, which are mostly initialized with random values, and then updated iteratively during training via backpropagation. The decoder part of the auto-encoder maps \mathbf{h}^3 to the reconstruction \mathbf{x}' in the same shape with \mathbf{x} as formalised in (3):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}^{2'} &= \sigma'(\mathbf{W}^{2'} \mathbf{h}^3 + \mathbf{b}^{2'}) \\ \mathbf{h}^{1'} &= \sigma'(\mathbf{W}^{1'} \mathbf{h}^{2'} + \mathbf{b}^{1'}) \\ \mathbf{x}' &= \sigma'(\mathbf{W}^{0'} \mathbf{h}^{1'} + \mathbf{b}^{0'}) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma', (\mathbf{W}^{2'}, \mathbf{W}^{1'}, \mathbf{W}^{0'})$, and $(\mathbf{b}^{2'}, \mathbf{b}^{1'}, \mathbf{b}^{0'})$ are activation function, weight matrices and bias vectors respectively for the decoder. Autoencoders are trained to minimise reconstruction errors (e.g. squared errors) that are usually referred to as the "loss" and expressed as in (4):

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'\|^2 \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{x} is often averaged over some input training set in batches.

3.3 | Metrics

In our formulation of the problem, we use the following definitions in our metric formulations:

- True Positive (TP) can be defined as *malign* (non-*malign*) case correctly identified as *malign* (non-*malign*) case .
- False Positive (FP) can be defined as non-*malign* (*malign*) case incorrectly identified as *malign* case (non-*malign*).
- True Negative (TN) can be defined as non-*malign* (*malign*) case correctly identified as non-*malign* (*malign*) case.
- Finally False Negative (FN) can be defined as *malign* (non-*malign*) case incorrectly identified as non-*malign* (*malign*) case.

Accuracy is an important metric in balanced datasets. However, our dataset is unbalanced and other metrics such as *Recall*, *Precision*, etc. become more important score to test the performance of the various models. In our study, *Recall* metric is trying to answer “What proportion of actual cases (*malign* and non-*malign*) was identified correctly?”. It is the ability of the classification model to find all the relevant cases within the data points in the dataset. High *Recall* relates to low False Negative Rate (FNR).

Precision is trying to answer the question “What proportion of *malign* case (non-*malign*) identifications was actually correct?”. It is the ability of the classification model to identify only the relevant data points in the dataset. High *Precision* value relates to low False Positive Rate (FPR).

Precision-Recall is useful metric to measure the success of classification in case the classes are imbalanced. Precision-Recall (PR) curve shows the trade-off between the *Precision* and *Recall* for different threshold values. In a typical PR curve, *Precision* is plotted on the vertical axis, and *Recall* is plotted on the horizontal axis. High area under the PR curve represents high *Precision* and *Recall* values. In an ideal system, high *Precision* and *Recall* signifies that all returned classification results are labelled correctly. In a binary classification problem such as ours, *Recall* of the positive class (*malign* cases) is *Sensitivity* and the *Recall* of the negative class (non-*malign* cases) is *Specificity*. Another metric that is considered during numerical evaluations is *Balanced Accuracy* which is the average of *Sensitivity* and *Specificity*.

Note that there exists an inherent trade-off between *Recall* and *Precision* values where it is hard for a ML model to keep them both high (i.e. close to 1). When screening *malign* cases for cancer, FNs are more important than FPs. The reason is that it is much worse than saying a patient does not have *malign* case when that do instead of saying that the patient has it but it is later realized that they do not have *malign* case (i.e. cancer). For this reason, keeping *Recall* values high (more specifically *Sensitivity* in binary classification) is more important than high *Precision* values.

Since we have non-categorical values in the input (e.g. the span of the *AGE*, *SIZE*₁ and *SIZE*₂ variables exceed the range [0,1] as given in Table 1) in addition to categorical values, to evaluate the performance of auto-encoder network output, we use MSE as the loss function on the auto-encoder network output and target data (which is same with input data). The MSE loss expresses the *Accuracy*.

3.4 | Supervised Learning using SMOTE Oversampling for Imbalanced Dataset

Imbalanced datasets are common in health domain where only partial number of patients may have some rare disease conditions (minority class) out of all scanned patients. When an ML algorithm is trained with such an imbalanced dataset, the impact of minority class over the trained model is damped in general due to dominance of majority class. As a result of this, the model can not learn enough from minority class samples, which degrades the classification performance in terms of *Precision*, *Recall* and other metrics. For this reason, classification on imbalanced datasets need to be studied in detail before applying any ML techniques on these datasets. There are various techniques to improve the model performance in the presence of dataset. One of them is re-sampling the dataset either via under-sampling or over-sampling. In under-sampling, the samples from majority classes are removed. This is useful in cases when we have huge dataset. In over-sampling, more data samples are added for under-represented classes. This technique is useful when we have small dataset. In this paper, we utilize a well known technique called SMOTE which is an over-sampling method and hence performs data augmentation of minority datasets¹⁸.

By applying SMOTE, we create new synthetic samples for minority class based on k-nearest neighbor relations such that each new synthetic sample is constituted between two pre-existing k-nearest samples of minority class. Thus, the number of samples in minority class is augmented that paves the way for more effective learning from the minority class. Notice that the ratio of

FIGURE 4 t-SNE plot to visualize the dataset distribution in 2D projection for (a) original imbalanced training dataset. (b) balanced training dataset after SMOTE operation.

the samples between minority class and majority class is balanced only in the training dataset, while test dataset remains as in the original distribution to perform a fair performance evaluation.

To visualize the pre-processed data, we use t-SNE plot which projects high dimensional data into two dimensions. Fig. 4a shows the t-SNE plot where distribution of all original training samples in the dataset is plotted. The t-SNE plot shows the malign cases (in red) and non-malign cases (in green) where non-malign cases outnumber the malign cases. We can observe from this figure that the malign and non-malign cases cannot be adequately separated from each other using this projection method. We can also clearly observe the spatial nature of the severe class imbalance in the dataset from this scattered plot. On the other hand, Figure 4b shows the t-SNE plot distribution after the SMOTE oversampling. We can observe that using SMOTE oversampling methodology has increased the number of samples present under the category of minority malign cases to balance the number of malign and non-malign cases before training. The newly generated samples in Figure 4b are seen to follow specific patterns when their dimensions are reduced to two. This is due to being constituted between k-nearest neighbours of the original samples.

4 | EXPERIMENTAL SETTINGS

In this section, we describe the experimental settings, data collection process, healthcare dataset parameters and data statistics used for training as well as performance evaluation of the proposed methods in this section.

4.1 | Healthcare Dataset Description

For evaluation results, anonymous data is retrospectively collected offline from Thyroid Nodules dataset and transferred into the database for a period of 3 years and 6 months ranging from January 2016 to June 2019 in Turkey. However, patient samples are not daily and are sparsely distributed over the collection period and includes 99 unique days. The data is collected by the department of radiology and the validation of the US data is performed by the FNA pathology results. Usually, patients experience sore throat, swelling in the throat area, etc. Then, they apply to the hospital for their complaints. Later, an US is requested by the internal medicine doctor for the patients, if he/she deems necessary when having difficulties for diagnosis. US scan is applied to these patients by the radiology team. If there are signs of a malignancy risk for the nodule during US, this patient is asked to give an FNA sample. The statistical distributions of these patients who had both US and FNA results constitute the observed data. Some statistics information of the collected healthcare dataset used in our evaluations are given in Table 1.

The dataset is provided by the healthcare partner and consists of hundreds of patient samples (710 samples) collected during the process. Labels are also available in the considered dataset. Each patient profile is represented by a 21 dimensional feature vector. Table 2 shows all these features, their descriptions and the values of the features in the dataset. There are both male

TABLE 1 Collected health dataset statistics.

Total number of unique patients	636	Number of features (original)	21
Total Number of samples in dataset	710	Patient age (avg \pm std)	49.95 \pm 13.33
Total number of men/women in dataset	108/528	number of features (post-processing)	78
$Size_1$ (avg \pm std)	1.69 \pm 1.19	$Size_2$ (avg \pm std)	2.60 \pm 2.60
Obser. Sample Duration	99 days	Number of categorical features (original)	18

and female patients in the data collected, and there are also patients in different age groups. Especially, this wide range of age distribution is useful for generalizing the analysis.

In our dataset, data with less than 1% are labeled as *malign* (corresponding to an abnormal thyroid nodule) and the rest are labelled as *non-malign* (corresponding to a normal thyroid nodule). In this paper, we are mostly interested in identifying the *malign* labels correctly. Therefore, the dataset is unbalanced as the *malign* labels are “extremely rare” in our dataset (e.g. only 6 out of 636 are *malign* which accounts for only 0.95% of all dataset used in our paper). Accurate classification or detection of those extremely rare cases is quite challenging. For this reason, we resort to auto-encoder-based neural network classifier which is generally used for anomaly detection purposes. Instead in our problem solution, we build a simple dense layers auto-encoder for accurate classification of *malign* labels in our dataset.

We have divided the dataset into two sets: *malign* labelled and *non-malign* labelled. The *non-malign* labeled dataset is treated as normal condition. First, for training of auto-encoder, we will ignore the *malign* labelled dataset and concentrate on *non-malign* labelled dataset. After training, auto-encoder model has learned the features of the normal condition. As the *Accuracy* of the training of the auto-encoder increase, the new data arriving from normal dataset will be predicted as *non-malign* since the pattern or the distribution of the dataset will be similar. For this reason, the reconstruction error will become very small. In case, a new dataset (e.g. *malign* labelled) is fed into auto-encoder, the auto-encoder will produce large reconstruction error. As a result, we will be able to label those dataset having high reconstruction error as *malign* labelled. The procedure is similar to an anomaly detection scheme¹⁹.

TABLE 2 All features and their corresponding descriptions of the dataset

Feature	Description	Feature	Description	Feature	Description
Gender	—Male or female patients —Labelled as 1 or 0	Taller	—Indicates whether the length of the nodule is greater than its width	Tiroidit	—A general name for inflammation of the thyroid gland. —Points out inflammation no inflammation or heterogeneous structure.
Age	—Patients’ ages range from 19 to 89.	Acr2017	—American College of Radiology publication in 2017 ²⁰ —Classification for malignancy risk —Total points range from 0 to 11	Halo	—Existence of a ring structure around the nodule
Shape	—Shape of the Nodule. —Cases include normal, irregular and lobule like, echoic, etc.	Lap	—Means Lymphadenopathy —Indicates whether the nodule is abnormal or inconsistent in size	Acr Point	—Final scores of ACR —Total point range from 0 to 11
Calcific	—The accumulation of calcium salts in tissue. —Occurs normally in bones —Calcium can build up abnormally in soft tissue. —Causes tissue to harden. —Values range from 0 to 3	K-Tirads	—The reporting system of the Korean Society of Thyroid Radiology. ²¹ —Indicates the risk assessment of thyroid nodules by the ultrasound. —Provide stratification of the requirement for FNA. —Risk Levels range from 2 to 5	Ata2015	—American Thyroid Association published guidelines in 2015 —For adult patients with thyroid nodules and differentiated thyroid cancer ²² —Risk levels range from 1 to 5
Colour	—Color contrast level of the nodule in US relative to its surrounding —Values range from 0 to 4	EU-Tirads	—European thyroid association risk value for ultrasound malignancy ²³ —Risk levels range from 2 to 5	Margin	—Edge structure of the nodule —Distinct or indistinct
Solid Cystic	—Cystic nodules are mainly in liquid form. —Some are in solid form indicating anomaly. —Values range from 1 to 4	Size	—Corresponds to size of thyroid nodule in X-axis and Y-axis represented as $SIZE_1 \times SIZE_2$ —X-axis and Y-axis dimension values are marked as $SIZE_1$ and $SIZE_2$ respectively.	Patho_Risk	—Indicates the risk assessment value of the pathology —Risk levels range from 0 to 7
Spongy Structure	—Defines whether the tissue is spongy or not	Location	—Position of the nodule on the gland —Can be on the right lobe left lobe or on isthmus (in the middle)	class	—Represents final two distinct classes (<i>malign</i> or <i>non-malign</i>)

TABLE 3 A comparison of different assessment methodologies prepared by various health institutions.

	EU-Tirads	K-Tirads	ATA	ACR
Assessment Steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Categorize based on shape —An exception for highly risky level —Mark highly risky if one of the highly risky features exist 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Pre-categorize based on Solid Cystic status —Change risk levels based on the highly risky features 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Categorize based on the combination of shape and solid cystic status —For intermediate and highly risky, check the existence of HRFs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Assign points to each feature —Calculate total sum —Categorize based on total score
HRFs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Halo —Calcific —Margin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Taller —Calcific —Shape 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Margin —Taller —Calcific 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —No HRF definition
Risk Level-2 (Very Low)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Shape(Normal) —Spongiform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Partially Cystic —Spongiform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Partially Cystic —Spongiform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —2 points
Risk Level-3 (Low)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Shape (Isohyperechoic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Partially Cystic —Shape (Isohyperechoic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Partially Cystic —Shape (Isoechoic) or —Partially Cystic —Shape(Hyperechoic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —3 points
Risk Level-4 (Intermediate)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Shape (Mildly Hyperchoic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Partially Cystic —Shape (Isohyperechoic) —Has one of the HRFs or —Solid Cystic —Shape(Hyperechoic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Solid Cystic —Shape(Hyperechoic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —4 to 6 points
Risk Level-5 (High)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Shape (Hyperechoic) —Has one of the HRFs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Solid Cystic —Shape (Hyperechoic) —Has one of the HRFs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —Solid Cystic —Shape (Hyperechoic) —Has one of the HRFs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> —7 and more points

4.2 | Rule-Based Assessment Methods of Different Health Institutions

In the collected dataset, there are also features belonging to studies on methods of classifying US images for thyroid nodules created by different health institutions. However, these studies refer to rule-based classification. At the same time, the classification rules created by these institutions are the systems that are formed based on the experiences of the agreements among the institution's members. Therefore, each individual organization conducting thyroid research has different classification studies and assessment methods^{20,21,22,23}. In fact, as mentioned before, classification of thyroid nodules is a very complicated problem, therefore these institutions present different classification methods. For this reason, different interpretations have emerged by them. During our analysis, we have also enabled the ML algorithm to use the classification results of all these institutions.

A comparison summary of all the methods indicating the steps for assessment and risk level determination are presented in Table 3. In the ACR²⁰ method, a scoring is calculated for each detected feature based on US observations and then these scores are later added to calculate the final total score. The risk status of the nodule is categorized according to this total score. K-Tirads²¹, defines three High Risk Features (HRFs) (taller calcific, shape). In order to determine the risk levels, a pre-classification is performed according to the shape feature. Then, the risk level classified based on the existence of the HRFs. ATA²² is the oldest method that presents three HRFs (margin, taller, calcific). Similar to K-Tirads, firstly, risk levels are determined according to the shape and solid cystic condition. In the assessment method of EU-Tirads, there are three defined HRFs (halo, calcific, margin). Even if there exists one of these on the nodule, the nodule is directly evaluated in Risk Level 5 (namely, high risk). To determine the other risk levels in EU-Tirads²³ method, a distinction is made only by checking the solid cystic of the nodule. Since the focus of those rule-based methods rely on identification of malign nodes, definitions for the risk level-1 that indicates a benign nodule, are ignored by the institutions.

4.3 | Parameters

The objective of this paper is to detect extremely rare malign cases using the whole dataset. For this purpose, we need to carefully select the most appropriate parameters to fine tune our algorithms. During our pre-processing phase of generating training, validation and testing dataset, we first split the dataset into training and testing datasets using a 80% – 20% ratio. Later, we further split the training dataset into training and validation dataset again in a 80% – 20% ratio. Hence for the all the classification methods and auto-encoder-based semi-supervised learning method, 64% of the patient samples are used for model training (454 samples), 16% for validation (114 samples) and 20% for testing (142 samples). Each of the training, validation

and testing dataset includes two `malign` cases. Then for each training and validation dataset, `non-malign` and `malign` cases are split into two separate dataframes to be used as input to auto-encoder. Later, standard scaling (i.e. removing the mean and scaling to unit variance) is applied to numerical features (i.e. `AGE`, `SIZE1` and `SIZE2`) of the dataset.

There are two reasons for scaling. One reason is that some of the classification algorithms (e.g. KNN classifier, Support Vector Machine Classifier (SVC), etc.) are sensitive to the scales of the feature. Another reason is that gradient descent algorithms used in neural networks converge faster with feature scaling, which significantly reduces the computation time during training sessions. The categorized features are encoded as a one-hot vector to convert them into binary vector format, hence the categorized feature can only take combinations of values with a single “1” and all the others “0”. Before categorization, the number of features was 21. After categorization features are extracted, the new feature number of the dataset extends to 78. For all classification algorithms, during training GridSearchCV with 10-fold cross-validation is applied to find the best hyper-parameters and the same train and test datasets were utilized for fair comparisons.

After extensive evaluations, the selected architecture of the auto-encoder is selected to be a symmetrically network of 3 encoders and 3 decoders. The architecture contains 78-128-64-32-64-128-78 nodes, 40,910 total parameters and 540 neurons including output layers. At the final layer, ReLU activation function layer is set as output player to classify the features into two classes (`malign` and `non-malign`). Our neural network was built using the Keras Functional Application Programming Interface (API)²⁴. All operational nodes in the auto-encoder network are utilizing ReLU activation functions ($f(\cdot)$) which returns the value provided as input directly, or the value 0.0 if the input is 0.0 or less:

$$f(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{b}) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{x}, & \mathbf{x} > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{x} is a function of the weights and biases of the dense neural layer. In an auto-encoder neural network, 78 variables are the number of input variables, hence 78 becomes the number of output variables. Learning rate is selected to be $1e - 3$ for network parameters optimization in each epoch and batch size is 128 (that determines the number of samples of data to be seen before updating the weights and biases of deep neural networks). The training is set to 300 epochs. We use Adam as the gradient descent optimizer to optimize the auto-encoder neural network parameters in the direction of gradients. Note that more hidden layers can allow this auto-encoder network to encode more complex relationships between the features of the input vector.

After selecting the architecture, the training job is completed. The standardized training dataset and standardized validation dataset with `non-malign` cases are used for training the auto-encoder and calculating the MSE loss function respectively. The testing dataset contains both `malign` and `non-malign` cases which represent a real dataset.

Since the original dataset is imbalanced and training on imbalanced dataset may yield non-satisfactory results, we use SMOTE to balance the minority class of `malign` cases. For this we use `imblearn` python package to over-sample the minority class. Before oversampling with SMOTE, number of `malign` cases is 2 and `non-malign` cases are 450 i.e. a 1:225 class distribution exists in the training dataset. After oversampling with SMOTE, counts of `malign` and `non-malign` cases both become 450 in the training dataset.

5 | EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we detail the analysis results of the comparisons of the considered auto-encoder based neural network structure and other related classification algorithms where SMOTE method is utilized in the training dataset of the classification methods/

5.1 | Auto-encoder results

After the auto-encoder has been trained, we need to select cutoff threshold error value using the reconstruction error observations will be categorized as `non-malign` ones and above which will be classified as `malign` ones. This threshold can be determined based on the optimization use case studied. In the following, we show how auto-encoder reconstruction error can be used for the `malign`-case classification. As mentioned earlier if the reconstruction error is high, the data is classified as a `malign` case. For this reason, a threshold needs to be determined for distinguishing between high and low reconstruction errors. To identify the threshold, we use the validation set. Fig. 5 shows the *Precision* and *Recall* values for different selected threshold values calculated over the validation dataset. In our case, we want to detect `malign` cases, hence *Recall* (more specifically *Sensitivity*) is more important than *Precision*. Using this figure, we can decide that the most optimal threshold value (with a reasonable

FIGURE 7 Confusion matrix of (a) auto-encoder outputs obtained over test dataset. (b) RFC outputs obtained over test dataset after SMOTE operation on training dataset.

parameter that states a trade-off between *Recall* rate and *Precision* rate. A high threshold will improve model's *Recall* rate at the expense of its *Precision* rate, i.e. concentrating only on detecting the malignant cases. Conversely, a low threshold will increase the model's *Precision* rate, decreasing its *Recall* rate, i.e. decreasing the detection capabilities of the extremely rare malignant incidents. Note that adjusting the level of threshold that changes the detection capabilities of the auto-encoder based neural network model depends on the requirements obtained from the considered problem.

5.2 | Other classification algorithm results

In this section, we compare the performance of other classification algorithms such as DT, RFC, SVC (linear), Logistic Regression (LR), XGBoost and Gradient Boosting Tree (GBT). Fig. 7b shows the confusion matrix of RFC outputs obtained over test dataset after SMOTE operation on training dataset. By observing this confusion matrix, the *Precision* and *Recall* values (macro averaged) can be calculated to be 100% and 75% respectively. Fig. 7a shows that the RFC has learned to partially discern malignant cases successfully. We could predict 1 out of 2 malignant cases. This is 50% of *Sensitivity* rate which can be considered to be low for the considered use case in the health industry. On the other hand, we have truly classified all non-malign cases as non-malign, i.e. *Specificity* is 100% (FPR is 0%) which could lead to patient satisfaction with the results. Note that considering the recall and precision trade-offs discussed in Section 5.1, the auto-encoder based neural networks have higher flexibility than other classification algorithms to tune the detection capabilities for higher performance.

Table 4 shows above described classifiers' Accuracy, Precision, Recall, Sensitivity, Specificity, Balanced Accuracy and F1 scores using cross validations operation on training + validation dataset after SMOTE oversampling operation. We use *Repeated Stratified K-Fold cross validator* of sklearn with the number of folds selected to be 10 and number of times the cross-validator needs to be repeatedly selected to be 3. In Table 4, the balanced accuracy is defined as the average of recall obtained on each class. Note that accuracy metric is not an appropriate metric to be observed in an imbalanced dataset as of ours. For this reason in our classification algorithm outcomes, recall and balanced accuracy are important metrics to be monitored closely. From Table 4, we can observe that the best results are obtained using RFC with 1.0 recall, balanced accuracy and F1 scores which are also marked with bold values.

Table 5 shows different classifiers' test Accuracy, Precision (macro averaged), Recall (macro averaged), Sensitivity, Specificity, F1 (macro averaged) and AUC scores over test dataset after SMOTE operation on train dataset. Here, the term *macro average* means that the metrics are calculated for each class, and their unweighted mean is found. Note that in our considered scenario, detecting the rare malignant cases is very important and is our main focus in this paper. Therefore, *Recall* of the positive class (malign cases), i.e. *Sensitivity* becomes important. We can observe that auto-encoder based solutions gives

TABLE 4 Different classifiers' Accuracy, Precision, Recall, Balanced Accuracy and F1 scores using cross-validation operation on training + validation dataset after SMOTE oversampling operation.

Classifier	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Sensitivity	Specificity	Balanced Accuracy	F1
LR	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997
SVC	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997
DT	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997
GBT	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998
RFC	1.000	0.999	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
XGBoost	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998

TABLE 5 Different classifiers' test Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 and AUC scores over test dataset after SMOTE oversampling operation on train dataset.

Classifier	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1	AUC
LR	0.99	1.0	0.75	0.50	1.0	0.83	0.62
SVC	0.99	1.0	0.75	0.50	1.0	0.83	0.50
DT	0.99	1.0	0.75	0.50	1.0	0.83	0.75
GBT	0.99	1.0	0.75	0.50	1.0	0.83	0.97
RFC	0.99	1.0	0.75	0.50	1.0	0.83	0.73
XGBoost	0.99	0.75	0.75	0.50	0.99	0.75	0.97
Auto-encoder (no SMOTE)	0.97	0.64	0.98	1.0	0.96	0.71	0.99

FIGURE 8 Top 16 features and their corresponding feature importance values in bar chart for RFC.

the highest percentage (100% of *Sensitivity*) in comparison with other classification algorithm that are on the order of 50% (even after SMOTE oversampling operation during training which is expected to increase the test accuracy^{25,26}). In terms of *Specificity* that signifies the *Recall* of the negative class (non-malign cases), RFC, LR, SVC, DT and GBT all provide 100% accuracy whereas auto-encoder based model remains on 96%. Therefore, depending on the requirements and the trade-off between focusing on the detection of only malign case and detection of only non-malign cases, either auto-encoder based solution or other traditional classification algorithms after SMOTE oversampling can be utilized.

Classification algorithms such as DT, RFC XGBoost also provide feature importance values. Fig. 8 shows the top 16 features and their importance bar chart graph for RFC which has a *Recall* value of 50% to detect malign cases. We can observe that the most important feature with an importance value of 0.11 is *PATHO_RISK_5* which represents the risk assessment value of the pathology with a score of 5. When we observe our dataset, we find that all 6 patients with malign cases have *PATHO_RISK* = 5, whereas 36 patients with non-malign cases also have *PATHO_RISK* = 5. The second most important feature is *Acr2017_5* which represents the rule based score of 5 obtained using the American College of Radiology's published methodology. The third most important feature with feature importance score of 0.10 is *ACRPOINT_7.0* which

represents final scores of ACR with a value of seven. The fourth one is *CALCIFIC_0* which represents the accumulation of calcium salts in tissue with score 0. The fifth one is *K – TIRADS_5.0* that represents the reporting system of the Korean Society of Thyroid Radiology with a value of five.

5.3 | Discussions on Results and Limitations of the Proposed Approach

In this section, we discuss some of the main outcomes of the numerical results and some of the challenges of using the proposed approaches.

1-) Rule-based approaches: We can cite an example of the rule-based nodule malignancy risk assessment systems belonging to these 4 health institutions (Korean *K–Tirads*, American *Ata2015*, European *EU–Tirads* thyroid associations and American college of radiology publication *Acr2017*). For example, while *HALO* constitutes 1 additional point in the overall risk score for a nodule according to an institution, this feature may mean 0.5 or 0 additional points for another institution in the overall scoring. In the dataset of this article, we manually calculated the risk scores based on the methods described by each of these institutions and added the scores to the feature set. A very important point to note here is that according to the malignancy risk scoring methods of all these 4 health institutes, an US data can indicate the highest possibility of malignancy according to all 4 evaluation methods. However, the sample taken from the nodule with FNA can be found as benign according to pathology result, thus the estimation of all 4 systems can be wrong. We encountered situations like this in real patient treatments.

2-) Effect of features: Although RFC models have yielded low *Sensitivity* scores in comparison with auto-encoder based neural networks, its decision results can be explainable via feature importance plots. We can observe from Fig. 8 that 6 out of 16 most important features come from the outcomes of the previous rule based approaches. These results indicate that in addition to directly observed patient specific features from the samples such as *PATHO_RISK*, *AGE*, etc. Other additional features such as the outcomes of the rule based approaches and guidelines published by the association organizations are also helpful in making an appropriate classification. The *TIRODID* feature which is irrelevant in classification decision of the model is observed to not appear as an important feature in our RFC which was expected a-priori. In other words, the *TIRODID* feature is not evaluated as an important feature by 4 health institutions in terms of US image evaluation. We have added the *TIRODID* feature to our dataset for testing purposes of our proposed ML method's accuracy. As can be seen in the 8, the *TIRODID* feature did not create any discrimination in terms of identification. *CALCIFIC_0* feature with 0 score (small calcification) is also observed to be more important than *CALCIFIC_3* feature with 3 score.

Moreover, *GENDER* is found to be not important during the inference process. This result is expected in line with previous state-of-art²⁷ where *GENDER* is demonstrated to be irrelevant. On the other hand, based on the domain expertise *LAP* and *TALLER* features were expected to be important features which did not appear in the top 16 most important feature list of Fig. 8. At the same time, *COLOR* is one of the distinguishing features of detecting the malign cases US which turned out to be the 16'th most important feature. We assume that one of the reasons that these features did not appear in the top feature importance list would be the addition of new features of the rule based approach, i.e. the outcomes of the American, European and Korean Thyroid Societies into the input vector which are already utilizing those features to make a decision.

3-) Hyper parameter tuning and dynamic threshold: The performance of neural network based models are sensitive to shifting hyper-parameters in domain-specific problems. One of the things that needs to be considered during hyper-parameter tuning of auto-encoder neural network parameters is to set a dynamic decision threshold value based on the arrival of new patient data. As given in Fig. 5, the threshold value can determine a good trade-off on metrics such as *Precision* and *Recall*. However, such thresholds are selected based on the currently available validation dataset and if new data arrives to the validation dataset, the old selected threshold may be invalid. For this reason, the frequency of updates on the selected model can vary depending on the arrival of new patient data into the validation data. Solutions such as active/continuous learning can help to accommodate new data with the potential to improve training life-cycle.

4-) Comparisons with traditional approaches: Even though the performance improvements of Deep Learning (DL) based methods can be superior to traditional ML based approaches in most of the scenarios after appropriate hyper-parameter tuning and several iterative optimization, there are also some limitations of using the proposed DL based neural network approach (using auto-encoders) compared to more traditional classification methods. First of all, developing a DL model that meets certain requirements of a product/service can necessitate combinatorial search of parameters, variables, etc. which can be difficult as the model becomes more complex. There is an inherent trade-off between the complexity of models and generalizability to new datasets in DL-based systems which needs special attention during model building process. Moreover, inherent randomness and stochastic nature with the DL based systems and algorithms (built to avoid being stuck with sub-optimal saddle points) can make

it hard to produce stable and reproducible results unless running very large amounts of experiments. Second, the interpretability of the DL based model is another issue and concern for future research. For example, RFC can yield feature importance values but this is not the case for DL algorithms currently. Third, in comparison with traditional ML approaches such as RFC, DT classifiers, etc., as model complexity of auto-encoders increases with more deep layers, hyper-parameters, etc, it can need a huge amount of training time in resource-constrained environments which is a limitation in terms of computation cost. Hence, hyper-parameter selection requires resource-heavy techniques as well as hardware-aware optimization. Fourth, after model deployment, the model needs to be updated due to concept drift constraints hence additional Artificial Intelligence (AI)/ML infrastructure that monitors and performs continuous delivery of the model should be established. Last, DL based methods require large amounts of data to function optimally. Otherwise, the performance gains obtained via DL based methods are comparable to traditional ML based approaches, e.g. using small amount of data²⁸. However, in the healthcare domain, it is not always easy to collect large amounts of dataset especially when the privacy of the patients are involved during the data collection process. At the same time, there are also recent approaches that show that in problems with scarce training samples and without data augmentation, low-complexity neural networks can perform comparably well or better than state-of-the-art architectures²⁹.

6 | CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we considered the problem associated with detection of extremely rare malignant cases in Thyroid Nodules using an anonymous healthcare dataset. We used a real-world dataset collected offline from 636 patients in 99 unique days over the course of 3 years and 6 months, ranging from January 2016 to June 2019, in Turkey. In addition to the texture feature data of the US in our own dataset, we have also included the scores of different assessment methods created by different health institutions (e.g. Korean society of thyroid radiology, American thyroid association, European thyroid association). For detection of extremely rare malignant cases, we have used auto-encoder-based neural network which is a semi-supervised deep learning approach that is trained on non-malignant cases and tested by passing the test dataset to the trained auto-encoder-based neural network to detect malignant cases. We have also compared the proposed approach with classical classification algorithms (RFC, GBT, LR, etc.) that are SMOTE over-sampled due to imbalance in the training dataset. Our experimental results revealed that the auto-encoder based neural network model can result in an average *Recall* score of 0.98 and a *Sensitivity* score of 1.00 for detecting malignant and non-malignant cases from the healthcare dataset outperforming the other compared classification algorithms that are trained with SMOTE oversampling method.

Extensions of this work are ongoing in terms of improving our dataset. Our goal for future studies is especially to focus on cases where all four institutions' risk scores show the highest risk and all of them are mistaken at the result of FNA pathology. According to our observations, concentrating on such rare cases and using ML techniques in this direction will make a significant difference for thyroid nodule identification.

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